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D1.4 Region-Specific Social Innovation and Community Energy Approaches with an Application Potential in Biogas

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1. Executive Summary

This report builds upon previous research presented in the already submitted deliverables D1.1, D1.2 and D1.3 and **explores social innovation triggers to increase the likelihood of successful community biogas energy projects**. The specific challenge of this document is to **identify methods and approaches to stimulating the use of biogas across European communities**. By analysing the three targeted by ISABEL regions in Europe, which represent a ranging *maturity* in *biogas readiness*¹ from *mature* (Baden-Württemberg in Germany), *to intermediate* (Yorkshire and the Humber in UK) and *preliminary* (Central and Eastern Macedonia & Thrace in Greece), this report identifies some specific conditions that can facilitate future biogas projects in the future. Amongst these are:

- Technical knowhow, “role models” and stakeholder engagement
- Methods of generating positive social responses and increasing willingness for behavioural change
- Motivation mix (environmental and ecological motives, social and anthropocentric motives as well as economic)
- Policy framework and public acceptance

Further to the analysis of the 3-targeted regions of ISABEL, this report presents a **pool of methods for the successful adoption and diffusion of bioenergy initiatives**. Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of these bioenergy projects has been analysed, with some of the biggest **threats** being the lack of sufficient communication of the benefits of biogas community bioenergy, appropriate technologies within regions, initiator interest and financial security (due to changing policies and legislations or wider national financial conditions). Numerous models were reviewed and it has been identified that the **project models**, which reflect their essential characteristics, are hybrid, mixed and complex. **“Social franchising strategies” seem to** reflect the character and goals of community bioenergy initiatives triggered by social innovations.

Although there is no “single prescription for success” of a project, it has been highlighted that **promoting engagement through communicative participatory processes** can significantly raise awareness and public trust, which can thereafter lead to attracting investments for the given bioenergy community project. **Successful** community energy projects include the provision of a **motivation mix** that mostly target **social** (e.g. job opportunities) **and financial incentives** (e.g. energy ownership, tax-reliefs and subsidies) as well as of **environmental and regulation related ones**. Remarkably, while the availability of **technical** support of a bioenergy project may be necessary; it does not seem to offer a stand-alone incentive for its initiation, delivery and success.

Appropriate frameworks and models for taking communities from the condition of unawareness, to awareness, project evaluation, adoption, implementation and diffusion have been explored. A proposed **sequential approach to the successful initiation and enhancement of community bioenergy projects has been developed and presented**.

Overall, this report illustrates challenges and complexities of community bioenergy projects and has aimed to approach them through both **theoretical** (literature review) and **qualitative** methods (see also D1.3). Biogas communities are believed to promote a wider “common good” as their adoption, implementation and diffusion can offer valuable contributions to societal growth, economic sustainability and environmental “health” for today and the future.

¹ The latter “*biogas readiness*” has been developed by the INSEAD / ISABEL team to describe in a simple way the relative “*maturity in biogas*” and rate (mature, intermediate, preliminary) at which each selected region appears to use actively or be likely to use actively biogas in the future. This readiness depends upon interconnected factors, which may relate to national policies, governmental, investor needs, social, technical and other requirements.

2. Scope of the Document

ISABEL is a response to the global challenge of mitigating the detrimental effects of climate change by promoting renewable energy sources across Europe and more specifically the use of biogas. The specific challenge of this project is to **identify methods and approaches to stimulating the use of biogas across European communities**. Energy can either (i) be distributed within communities through top-down methods or (ii) communities can develop their own projects to benefit from biogas through bottom up approaches.

EU policies and governmental approaches currently show minimal support towards the EU-28 2020 action plans (NREAP²). **This report**, building on previous ISABEL research presented in the already submitted deliverables D1.1, D1.2 and D1.3, **explores social innovation triggers to increase the likelihood of community biogas energy projects**.

- D1.1 *“Social innovation and community energy best practices, methods and tools across Europe”*
- D1.2 *“Biogas landscape and specificities in the 3-targeted regions”*
- D1.3 *“Communities’ and stakeholders’ perceptions on biogas and its implications”*

Bioenergy projects and community energy initiatives may vary considerably (may be organized differently, using different methods, technologies or financial models) and **there is no “single prescription for success”**. The aim is to conclude with a pool of social innovation and community energy approaches, methods and tools with application potential on biogas in each of the targeted regions. That is by matching good practices with the opportunities and barriers identified, the regional operational contexts and specificities, and the stakeholders and communities’ perceptions.

In aiming to contribute positively towards a better understanding of successful methods and tools for future community biogas initiatives, ISABEL has selected and analysed three European regions, in Germany (Baden-Württemberg), the UK (Yorkshire and the Humber) and Greece (Central and Eastern Macedonia & Thrace). These regions represent a different **“biogas readiness”**. The latter term is developed by the INSEAD / ISABEL team to describe in a simple way the relative **“maturity in biogas” as a rating system** at which each selected region appears to **be mature, intermediately mature or preliminarily involved** in using biogas. This report highlights that the “biogas readiness” may depend upon interconnected factors, such as combinations of national policies, governmental, investor needs, social, technical and other requirements.

↳ **Germany** has the lowest unemployment rate in Europe. It has pioneered the development of bioenergy villages since the 1990s, and currently 179 bioenergy villages exist. Germany’s projects have been incentivized by positive financial incentives that were offered as part of public policy. These incentive schemes, however, are facing a downturn since 2014. **Baden-Württemberg in Mauenheim** hosts one third of the German bioenergy villages and is the focus of ISABEL’s German region.

↳ **The United Kingdom** has the second lowest unemployment rate after Germany and, since 2010, a growing policy provision of public and private community energy financial incentives. This legislation, however, seems to indicate an uncertain trend towards subsidies and tax reliefs, which also could put bioenergy initiatives on relatively unstable grounds. Recent cuts (2015-16) seem to impact on the financial viability of community energy projects. **Yorkshire and the Humber** is a regional community that is strongly orientated towards developing and generating its own bioenergy and is the focus of ISABEL’s UK region.

↳ **Greece** has the highest unemployment rate in Europe and the most difficult political conditions. This impacts public policy provision, which provides very minimal financial incentives towards the

² <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/renewable-energy/national-action-plans>
<http://www.eea.europa.eu/highlights/take-a-closer-look-at>

development of new bioenergy projects. Renewable energy projects depend predominantly on private initiatives, which mostly represent specific enterprise interests rather than community interests. **Central and Eastern Macedonia & Thrace** is a very slowly developing bioenergy region and is the focus of ISABEL's Greek region.

In this report, we have identified and explored ISABEL's 3-targeted regions' (i) **context & intervening conditions**, (ii) **causal conditions**, (iii) **approach, action and interaction strategy**, (iv) **methods & tools** and, (v) **consequences after the implementation of the bioenergy project**.

Next, the **strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats** of each project were identified and key barriers to their success highlighted. More specifically, it was shown that the **overall barriers** to the enhancement and diffusion of the regional projects were:

- (i) **Financial and governance related in Baden-Württemberg,**
- (ii) **Technical, financial and governance related in Yorkshire and the Humber, and**
- (iii) **Sustainability, social / community related, financial and governance related in Central and Eastern Macedonia & Thrace.**

It was recognised that although there is no "single prescription for success" of a project, some important **success factors** for community energy projects include a **motivation mix** of **social** (e.g. job opportunities) and **financial** incentives (e.g. energy ownership, tax-reliefs and subsidies) and thereafter of **environmental** and **regulation** related incentives. **Technical** issues of bioenergy projects would not seem to offer a stand-alone incentive for the initiation, delivery and success of a project. That is because community bioenergy projects target a social and environmental impact rather than just a technical proposition for an AD installation to serve a community.

In aiming to develop an appropriate framework in taking communities from the condition of unawareness, to awareness, project evaluation, adoption, implementation and diffusion, various **entrepreneurial models** have been explored. Moreover, a **sequential approach** to successful initiation and enhancement of community bioenergy projects has been developed and presented. This has highlighted the importance of **communication** for raising awareness in such projects. Thus, a **pool of methods and tools** that have been shown to increase **trust and awareness** amongst a community of individuals and or stakeholders are presented in this report. These methods, for instance can be based on workshops, tours, events, engagement of schools, online platforms and more.

Overall, this report has illustrated challenges and complexities of community bioenergy projects and has aimed to approach them through both **theoretical** (literature review) and **qualitative** methods (see also D1.3). Biogas communities are believed to promote a wider "common good". The surveys of ISABEL have shown particularly that in order to boost participation in biogas communities, the focus should be on the communal benefits and added value that this approach could bring to the communities as a whole. Finally, although communities and stakeholders may often seem to be attracted by the social and financial motives for their projects, rather than the anticipated ecological ones, we believe that community biogas project adoption, implementation and diffusion offer a potentially substantial contribution to societal growth, economic sustainability and environmental "health" for today and the future.

3. Introductory Framework

3.1 Bioenergy Challenge

In 1992 at the Rio Earth Summit it was announced for the first time that new ways should be identified in order to tackle climate change³. The so-called '*Rio Convention*' soon after adopted the **UN Framework on Climate Change** (UNFCCC) and set out a framework for the mitigation of greenhouse gases (GHGs)⁴. In 2015, the same questions persist with the **COP21 (2015 Paris Climate Conference)**, aiming to achieve a fruitful negotiation within the United Nations and targeting a universal and legally binding agreement on keeping global warming below 2°C.

Climate change poses one of the greatest contemporary environmental and socio-economic challenges worldwide. While its harmful results show no signs of significant decline, its impacts attract increasing global attention⁵. Mitigating the negative impacts of climate change was linked, in 2011, with the use of **low carbon renewable energy sources** by the *United Nations Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*⁶. However, to date, a majority of industrialised nations still use largely fossil fuels and nuclear power, which can harm natural ecosystems as well as societal health and sustainability⁷. EU-28 is still the third largest CO₂ emitter globally (3420 MTn of CO₂ emitted in 2014)^{8,9} while at the same time holding almost half of the renewable energy capacity worldwide (2012 figures stated this capacity was 44% of the global capacity excluding hydropower¹⁰). Thus, the European Commission has targeted a new goal for more energy efficient and competitive approaches to power generation (for electricity, heating and transportation) by 2050. One of these approaches, which can offer significant benefits to the low carbon economy, is bioenergy. The bio-economy¹¹ currently represents a €2.4 billion market in Europe. **Using bioenergy can benefit environmental sustainability (by reducing fossil-based and imported energy sources) and social welfare** (by providing knowledge, incentives for innovation as well as by increasing job opportunities, with a 2020 target of creating approximately 600,000 new jobs via the renewable energy sector).¹²

Bioenergy produced by biomass is one the most important and readily available renewable energy sources. It is a derivative of organic matter, such as plants, oilseeds, agro-waste and urban organic waste and can be a better alternative to oil, gas and the use of fossil fuels.¹³ Although biogas has been used since the ancient times (by Persian, Chinese and Assyrian people), a **lack of public awareness and technical skills as well as low provision of financial incentives have resulted in only limited use**. Some successful examples of the use of biogas in Europe can be noted, such as: **(i)** in Exeter (UK) in 1895, where street lights and homes were powered from sewage, wood gas and coal, **(ii)** in Sweden where a biogas-powered train-service has operated since 2005, and **(iii)** in Greece, where the EBZ sugar industry has converted 2 out of its 5 factories (in Thrace and Thessaly) to produce bioethanol since 2008.¹⁴

In 2013, according to Eurostat, **renewable energy sources were reported to be 11.8% of the total inland energy consumption of the EU-28**.¹⁵ The proportion of **biomass and renewable waste accounted for 64.2%**

³ <http://www.cop21paris.org/about/cop21>

⁴ <http://www.cop21paris.org/about/cop21>

⁵ <http://www.wri.org/indc-definition>

⁶ <http://srren.ipcc-wg3.de/report>

⁷ <http://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/4/2/244>

⁸ <http://infographics.pbl.nl/website/globalco2-2015>

⁹ https://royalsociety.org/~media/Royal_Society_Content/policy/projects/climate-evidence-causes/climate-change-evidence-causes.pdf

¹⁰ http://www.europarl.europa.eu/atyourservice/en/displayFtu.html?ftuld=FTU_5.7.4.html

¹¹ <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2211464515000305>

¹² <http://www.cost.eu/module/download/54801>

¹³ http://www.europarl.europa.eu/atyourservice/en/displayFtu.html?ftuld=FTU_5.7.4.html

¹⁴ <http://ecology-salonika.org/2009/?p=393>

¹⁵ http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Renewable_energy_statistics

of the total renewable energies across EU-28 in 2013¹⁶. In 2015, the *biofuel barometer* suggested that, during 2013-14, the EU-28 has seen a 6.1% increase in biofuel consumption.¹⁷ However, according to *EurObserv'ER*, this increase does not represent a growing trend.¹⁸ This means that even though in 2013, 13.4 (Mtoe) of biogas were produced, which is 1.2 (Mtoe) more than 2012, the use of biogas in the near future is set to decline.

Figure 1. Electricity generated from renewable sources proportionally to the gross energy consumption across the EU-28 in 2013

Source: Eurostat (tsdcc330)¹⁹

(*) 2003: not available.

Figure 2. EU-28 electricity generated from renewable energy sources in the period 2003–2013

Source: Eurostat (nrg_105a) and (tsdcc330)²⁰

¹⁶ http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Renewable_energy_statistics

¹⁷ <http://www.eurobserv-er.org/biofuels-barometer-2015>

¹⁸ <http://www.eurobserv-er.org/biogas-barometer-2014>

¹⁹ http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Renewable_energy_statistics

²⁰ http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Renewable_energy_statistics

Associated with the sector decline are EU policy changes impose limitations on financial incentives for the use of energy crops. At the same time, the *EU National Renewable Energy Action Plan* sets a target for 2020 **to double the bioenergy and biofuel contribution** in the bioenergy supply chain.²¹ The anticipated increase in the shares of renewable energy (proportionally to the gross energy production) across EU-28 from 2013 to 2020 can be summarized in the diagram below (from Eurostat).²² **As biomass can offer a significant boost in renewable energy production and consumption, building on bioenergy initiatives is vital** (e.g. by increasing social awareness and acceptance and energy efficiency).

(*) Legally binding targets for 2020.

(*) 2013: estimate.

Figure 3. Anticipated increase in the shares of renewable energy (proportionally to the gross energy production) across EU-28 from 2013 to 2020

Source: Eurostat (t2020_31)²³

Several governmental policies and bio-based community strategies should be combined through top-bottom and bottom-up initiatives.²⁴ Thus, **identifying methods and recommendations for effective sustainable growth require social innovations and a new approach towards a European bio-economy** (COM(2002)60).²⁵ There is need to develop strategic action plans to support innovation towards bioenergy use. Social innovation is a particularly applicable method in tackling such global goals and achieving societal behavioural changes towards sustainability and ‘public good’.²⁶

²¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/renewable-energy/national-action-plans>

²² http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Renewable_energy_statistics

²³ http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Renewable_energy_statistics

²⁴ <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2211464515000305>

²⁵ https://www.insead.edu/facultyresearch/centres/insic/home/about_us.cfm

²⁶ Clinton, L. & Whisnant, R. (2014), *Model Behavior: 20 Business Model Innovations for Sustainability*, SustainAbility Ltd. (www.sustainability.com)

3.2 Overview of the Region-Specific Bioenergy Project Analysis

Analyzing the three ISABEL regions aims to provide a better understanding of the main factors, methods and tools to deliver future successful bioenergy projects. The regions analyzed by ISABEL are illustrated in the map on the left: Baden-Württemberg in Germany, Yorkshire and the Humber in the UK, and Central and Eastern Macedonia & Thrace in Greece. These regions are analyzed for their strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats as current and/ or prospective bioenergy communities

Figure 4. ISABEL target areas
(Source: ISABEL deliverable D1.3).

What is a Bioenergy Community?

Bioenergy communities are generally small communities in rural areas that rely on the use of biomass obtained locally and not imported or transported great distances. In these villages, district electricity for heating and/or for transportation can be generated, providing energy self-sufficiency (i.e. totally or partially free from external energy grids). There are numerous examples across Europe of bioenergy villages. Two successful examples are the German Jünde bioenergy village (near Göttingen) and the Baden-Württemberg (in Mauenheim)²⁷. The latter is one of ISABEL's targeted region for exploration.

Bioenergy village initiatives offer a number of strengths and weaknesses.²⁸ **Major strengths** are that bioenergy (i) reduces the risk of harmful waste gas releases in the environment, (ii) offers affordable community energy and (iii) provides alternative provisions for transportation fuels. In addition, it strengthens the local economy as well as enables the development of opportunities for new jobs. A key **weakness** of community bioenergy systems is that, for the system to be profitable, a majority of the local community is required to use bioenergy.²⁹ In addition, the amount of biomass production may differ considerably from year to year and thus may give an impression that the biogas initiative offers an unsafe investment.³⁰

²⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bioenergy_village

²⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bioenergy_village

²⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bioenergy_village

³⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bioenergy_village

Regional Analysis Method

The analysis of the three ISABEL target communities will follow the structure proposed for qualitative research by Strauss and Corbin (1996).³¹ This is a simple qualitative research model, which focuses on the:

- **Context & Intervening Conditions**
- **Causal Conditions**
- **Approach, Action and Interaction Strategy**
- **Methods & Tools**
- **Consequences after the Implementation of the Bioenergy Project**

Figure 5. Model for analysing renewable energy projects, as developed by Strauss and Corbin (1996)³²

³¹ Strauss, A.; Corbin, J. *Grounded Theory: Grundlagen Qualitativer Sozialforschung*; Beltz, Psychologie Verlags Union: Weinheim, Germany, 1996.

³² Strauss, A.; Corbin, J. *Grounded Theory: Grundlagen Qualitativer Sozialforschung*; Beltz Psychologie Verlags Union: Weinheim, Germany, 1996.

3.3 Social Innovation Community Bioenergy Initiatives

3.3.1 Germany: Baden-Württemberg

Context & Intervening Conditions: Since 1990, Germany has focused on biogas for energy production by providing competitive public provision. This has empowered 600 renewable energy cooperatives and the involvement of multiple stakeholders (see Figure 5) in the generation of local community-owned energy.³³ Some 41,000 new jobs are linked with the biogas production sector³⁴ and around 4.6% of the total electrical power of Germany is produced annually by biogas. Across the European nations, Germany has taken a leading role in developing **bioenergy villages**. Over the last 23 years, Germany has provided incentives for a higher involvement in bioenergy initiatives. However, recent changes to the National “Renewable Energy Sources Act” (EEG 2014), have introduced challenges for biogas. Limits have been imposed on the development of new biogas projects, with impacts on the previously growing biogas stakeholder interests.

Figure 6. Baden-Württemberg in Germany
(Source: ISABEL deliverable D1.3)

Figure 7. Baden-Württemberg in Germany
(Source³⁵)

Figure 8. Baden-Württemberg in Germany, level of connections and stakeholders' involvement in the region: Interview based result
(Source: ISABEL deliverable D1.3)

Causal Conditions: The EEG 2014 limits in incentives for renewable energy projects in Germany were imposed simultaneously with the new 2020 EU target for renewable energy use. However, given the need to secure energy and mitigate the effects of climate change, new ways should be identified to promote biogas production in Germany without the need of more governmental provisions. Currently, under public schemes based on government driven incentives, there are more than 179 bioenergy villages developed.

Learning from the strengths, weakness and opportunities experienced in **Baden-Württemberg** (Mauenheim district of Tuttlingen; developed in 2009), which is one of four of the most successful bioenergy regions in Germany, could provide a better understanding of the successful methods in community bioenergy production more generally. Baden-Württemberg hosts currently 53 bioenergy villages, a third of the national total.³⁶ It includes 400 inhabitants and involves the use of 148 buildings.

Approach, Action and Interaction Strategy: There are various **models and partnerships** in Baden-Württemberg. The diagram of Figure 5 (for more on the image please see, D1.3 report) illustrates the complex web of stakeholder connections in the Baden-Württemberg, which has empowered successful bioenergy projects. “Regional management agencies and organizations”, “Intermediaries” are the two most active stakeholders for biogas in the region. “Agriculture and Forestry” groups follow. Local biomass providers, authorities, energy suppliers and grid owners also are highly involved in biogas initiatives. **Cooperation** overall leads NGOs, SMEs, farmers, energy suppliers and new cooperatives to work together and work jointly on their ventures for a **wider “common good”**.

³³ <https://www.eonenergy.com/for-your-business/community-energy/what-is-community-energy>

³⁴ Fachagentur Nachwachsende Rohstoffe e.V., ‘Biogas in Deutschland 2015’, 2015.

³⁵ <http://www.bioenergiesdorf-mauenheim.de/>

³⁶ Fachagentur Nachwachsende Rohstoffe e.V., ‘Bioenergiesdörfer - Wege Zum Bioenergiesdorf’, accessed 15 April 2016, <http://www.wege-zum-bioenergiesdorf.de/bioenergiesdoerfer>

Methods & Tools: The main feedstock in the Baden-Württemberg bioenergy village is wood chips, which are used predominately for heating purposes. Recent calculations suggest that about 1900 tn of CO₂ per year are not released in the environment because of bioenergy use. While the region is predominantly using biogas, some energy is supplemented by solar power. The **partnerships** that have empowered the successful bioenergy projects are: biogas farmers, administrative officers, NGOs (working on environmental projects), forestry officers, private businesses, energy providers, biogas organizations, intermediaries and investors. An important method of initiating and enhancing bioenergy incentives in Baden-Württemberg has been based on **awareness and acceptance raising techniques**. These include:

- A wide diversity of **bioenergy activities** in the regions of Baden-Württemberg and Lake Constance
- **Bioenergy-tours** through excursions to existing successful bioenergy projects, which act as “role-models” for future projects (see more on the idea of providing “role models” in D1.1 report)
- Bioenergy **exhibition, local information events and articles** in the press
- **Conferences and workshops**

Consequences after the Implementation of the Bioenergy Project: Although it covers only 2.8% of the annual electricity demand by the use of biogas, civic participation and engagement in the region is high as the local population is, **(i) aware of the beneficial effects of bioenergy communities (e.g. community energy self-sufficiency, increased job opportunities, empowered re-investments) and (ii) has developed a sense of social responsibility**. Nonetheless, the Baden-Württemberg bioenergy initiatives in some cases also created conflicts, such as competition with other energy suppliers. It should be noted that the region is among the wealthiest in Europe, with one of the lowest unemployment rates.

3.3.2 United Kingdom: Yorkshire and the Humber

Figure 10. Yorkshire & Humber in the UK
(Source: ISABEL deliverable D1.3)

Strategies for a low carbon industrial future in Yorkshire and the Humber

Figure 9. Low Carbon Hub in Yorkshire and the Humber³⁷

Context & Intervening Conditions: The UK is second in biogas production in Europe³⁸ and during the last 5 years, more than 5,000 community energy initiatives have been developed. Although bioenergy initiatives in the UK have been active mostly during the last few years, a significant number of biogas plants has been built. Remarkably, in the period 2005-2015, the total biogas energy capacity increased, from 2 MWe to 260MWe.³⁹ Local authorities have supported these actions through provision of financial relief and subsidies for the promotion of the development of a **new alternative energy marketplace using bio-methane** as a domestic biogas. This has offered heating to around 350,000 UK households. UK bioenergy projects are promoted mainly through top-down activities (government driven). Although the economy has been facing a recession since 2009, the UK Department of Energy & Climate Change⁴⁰ strives to offer guidance for local communities that wish to generate and manage their own energy. This guidance focuses on community energy strategies and provides information on, for instance, **community-owned electricity generation** through renewable energy including biogas. Community energy is pursued as well by social enterprises such as the “Low Carbon Hub” in Oxfordshire.⁴¹ This has created **closed-loop** energy production (more on the term “closed-loop production” can be found in D1.1 report), which re-invests 100% of its surplus in its continuously growing renewable energy production. Overall, the EU and the UK Government pursue bioenergy and biofuel strategies with the aim to promote (i) rural development, (ii) diversity and security in energy supplies, as well as (iii) mitigation of the negative effects of climate change.⁴² However, producing biofuels seem to be more expensive than petrol or diesel. Thus the EU Biofuels Directive and UK Renewable Transport Fuels Obligation (RTFO) have set minimum

standards that encourage the use of the cheapest available biofuels (i.e. bioethanol, produced by starch and sugar, and biodiesel, produced by oil crops).⁴³ Existing infrastructure in **Yorkshire and the Humber** as well as the level of available feedstock, suggest that this region offers a strong potential for future biogas and biofuel developments.⁴⁴

Causal Conditions: Since 2010, studies have examined the plausibility of bioenergy projects in the UK and have shown that biomass can significantly benefit the renewable energy production of the nation in the long-term.⁴⁵ This research was carried out based on the MARKAL modelling system⁴⁶ and suggested additionally that a diversification of the energy markets, feedstock and uses (e.g. farmers focusing on crops that can produce biofuels) would be needed for future successful bioenergy projects.⁴⁷ More specifically,

³⁷ <https://www.tuc.org.uk/sites/default/files/LowcarbonindustrialstrategiesYH.pdf>

³⁸ EurObserv'ER, 'The State of Renewable Energies in Europe (Edition 2015) 15th Report', accessed 1 April 2016, <http://www.eurobserv-er.org/15th-annual-overview-barometer>

³⁹ Department of Energy & Climate Change. 2015. Digest of UK Energy Statistics (DUKES).

⁴⁰ <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/community-energy>

⁴¹ <http://www.lowcarbonhub.org>

⁴² <http://www.lgyh.gov.uk/dnlds/Biofuels%20Summary.pdf>

⁴³ <http://www.lgyh.gov.uk/dnlds/Biofuels%20Summary.pdf>

⁴⁴ <http://www.lgyh.gov.uk/dnlds/Biofuels%20Summary.pdf>

⁴⁵ Jablonski, S., et al. (2010). The role of bioenergy in the UK's energy future formulation and modelling of long-term UK bioenergy scenarios. *Energy Policy*, 38 (10), 5799-5816.

⁴⁶ <http://www.bio-energy.co.uk/index.html>

⁴⁷ Jablonski, S., et al. (2010). The role of bioenergy in thUK's energy future formulation and modelling of long-term UK bioenergy scenarios. *Energy Policy*, 38 (10), 5799-5816.

they have noted the importance of "securing feedstock quantity and quality, the availability of infrastructure required to support the growth in biomass use, [and] local and regional market dynamics" (Jablonski et al. 2010, p.5813).⁴⁸ UK woodland, especially in South Yorkshire (which is included in ISABEL's target region) may seem to restrict the existing biomass sector.⁴⁹ According to the AEA (2010), an increase in the bioenergy boiler sector is anticipated, from an existing capacity (2012; see Figure 8) of 2,800MW to 7,600MW in 2020.⁵⁰ According to the Forestry Commission in 2008, the UK faces a limited biomass market supply chain. Thus the UK Government and Forestry Commission have been aiming to create a new wood related UK supply chain.⁵¹

Approach, Action and Interaction Strategy: ISABEL focuses its further analysis on the **Yorkshire and the Humber** region. This region hosts a range of renewable energy installations and contributes to the UK's low carbon strategy through bio-based developments in the energy sector. A special characteristic of this regional development is that it **involves expertise in waste-to-resource innovations**. It also includes 13 operational anaerobic digestion plants using manure or slurry, crops, food waste, crop waste and other additional waste feedstock annually. Achieving a behavioural change towards biomass production has therefore been anticipated in the area of Yorkshire and the Humber. Thus partnerships were established between a non-profit organization that developed (operating the AD system; LEAP), a community centre and an environmental trust (hosting the AD system in their premises). Thereafter, government grants were fundamental for the financing of the construction and the initial operation of the system. Through a new **gate fee system** implemented for waste collection and treatment, energy bills of the hosting centres were reduced, and incomes for educational and training activities as well as pop up cafés and restaurant were regulated.

Methods & Tools: In the case of the Yorkshire and the Humber region, two main methods were followed in producing community bioenergy. The first, involved a digester being installed at an **environmental charity** premises. The community was mainly involved in developing **educational activities**. The second method included a digester being installed at a **community centre**. This involved multiple community groups who were housed in the centre. The community members therefore were also **directly engaged** with local **community commercial activities**, which included them working in the collection and treatment of their local waste. Additional **raising awareness and engagement** in the bioenergy initiatives were achieved through (i) **School activities** (including visits to plants in order to increase understanding of key technical digester features as well as issues of bio-economy), (ii) **Training activities through continuing professional development (CPD)**, (iii) **Showcasing "role models" of local closed-loop economies**, which indicated how community AD can provide a whole new value chain with incomes beyond the energy generation.

Consequences after the Implementation of the Bioenergy Project: In this project, all community members were allowed access to the communal facilities. The biogas produced is being used by the **local café as well as a restaurant** and all group members have been exposed to the activities of the centre as well as to the related technologies. The procedure offered an increased **awareness** of the community energy process and has attracted additional external interest. Overall, the Yorkshire and the Humber project succeeded in **raising awareness and a sense of social responsibility**. It increased **job opportunities as well as developed educational activities for schools around biogas**. As the project progressed, it finally also promoted the development of local enterprises and a rewarding circular bio-economy.

⁴⁸ <http://www.bio-energy.co.uk/index.html>

⁴⁹ DEFRA (2007). *UK Biomass Strategy*. Defra.

⁵⁰ AEA (2010). *Analysis of Renewables Growth to 2020*. London, DECC.

⁵¹ Forestry Commission (2008). *Woodfuel supply chain: a scoping study*. [online]." www.forestry.gov.uk/fr/INFD-8AGCCQ

3.3.3 Greece: Central and Eastern Macedonia & Thrace

Figure 11. Central and Eastern Macedonia & Thrace in Greece
(Source: ISABEL D1.3 Report)

Figure 12. 2003 TNS®-biomass plant Pirow
(Source: HELECTOR⁵³)

Context & Intervening Conditions: In Greece, the biogas sector develops in a relatively unstable financial market, which impacts directly on growth and investments. Biomass contributes currently about 0.6% of the total renewable energy (which provided 17% of the total national energy consumption in 2012). Some 61% of Greece's primary energy is imported (of which 44% is petrol and 13% is natural gas), whereas 39% is generated nationally (of which 77% is lignite and 22% is renewable energy; for more information see D1.2 & D1.3 report).

Currently, although anaerobic digestion is carried out for waste management, there is no appropriate infrastructure developed by the Greek Public Gas Corporation (DEPA) to provide biogas through the existing natural gas energy grid. Biogas plants in Greece offer a capacity of 44.13MWe and operate at solid waste landfills (SWL) and municipal wastewater treatment plants (MWTP)⁵².

There are three main co-generation biogas plants in Greece, (i) in Ano Liossia (Attica) operating at solid waste landfills with a 23.4 MWe capacity, (ii) in Psyttaleia (Saronic Gulf, Piraeus) operating at municipal wastewater treatment plants with a 11.4 MWe capacity, and (iii) Tagarades (Thessaloniki) operating at solid waste landfills with a 5 MWe capacity. Finally, the relative lack of public provision for biogas production has impacted negatively on private incentives for community biogas generation. This has led private incentives to focus predominantly on individual organizational needs and not on

community related ones. Hence, bioenergy initiatives (biomass-biogas) in Greece are realized through private investments (farmers, breeders and food processing industries), and do not include community energy characteristics (as explained further below).

Causal Conditions: Central and Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, is a large region in Greece, which includes 3 administrative districts. Their population is about 2.5 million and suffers high unemployment rates (about 24%: Central Macedonia 25.4% and Eastern Macedonia and Thrace 22.7%; 4th Quarter 2015 data). At the same time, the economy is based significantly on rural activities. More than half of all cattle breeding in Greece (the waste of which offers a basic feedstock for biogas production) exists in this area. Currently, the overall electricity produced from biogas in Central and Eastern Macedonia and Thrace accounts for 1,07% of the total electricity consumption (2012 calculations).

Approach, Action and Interaction Strategy: There is a small number of investment partners in Central and Eastern Macedonia and Thrace. It consists of four cattle farmers (20% share each), and the Ergo-planning Business Development & Consulting Services Company (major activities relate to the agricultural sector). The latter has developed several arrangements with local feedstock providers.

Methods & Tools: Raising awareness, trust and active social engagement in the bioenergy initiative, was achieved through the *Lagadas Biogas SA* private investment initiative. The method followed was though increased **communication**. This communication has changed perceptions of biogas. In 2009, for instance, the local communities of Lagada expressed fears about the potential installation of a biogas plant in their region. In some cases lack of understanding also created social conflicts. This was due to a general lack of knowledge regarding the operation and characteristics of such projects. **Comprehensive and continuous**

⁵²http://www.export-erneuerbare.de/EEE/Redaktion/DE/Downloads/Publikationen/Praesentationen/2016/120531-im-ifat-10-griechenland.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=2

⁵³ <http://www.lignite.gr/events/5.pdf>

information provision, (consecutive meetings with local community members and authorities, interviews in local radios and newspapers) enabled a **realization of the benefits of biogas plants in their region, at a local community and overall environmental scale** (e.g. new jobs, better management of environmentally dangerous residues). Thereafter an increasing interest of local breeders and food industries to provide the plant with their feedstock was observed.

Consequences after the Implementation of the Bioenergy Project: The current economic condition in Greece has impacted negatively on public funding for biogas projects. However, the economic downturn has also created an increased need for alternative energy marketplaces and the use of low carbon sources, such as biogas. This can generate income and/or reduction in the price of basic goods (like electricity and heating). It need not be a top-down approach, as related bottom-up community initiatives in several other sectors (e.g. agriculture, education, transport, etc.) have been taking place currently in Greece. It may therefore be possible that the current economic recession may be better addressed by building communities and local-based initiatives and partnerships for biogas. Viable scheme have also been shown **to raise awareness and a sense of social responsibility** in Greece and the targeted ISABEL region specifically. Such schemes can **create new job opportunities**, a potentially important contribution given the high unemployment rate in Greece.

3.4 Regional Summary Table

Based on the information presented in paragraph 2.1, the diagram below presents a simple schematic illustration of the biogas maturity readiness of the 3 targeted regions, as it is understand it in this analysis.

NATIONAL INFORMATION			
Country Name	Germany	United Kingdom	Greece
Rating Biogas Readiness [*]	High (since 1990 [1])	Intermediate (since 2010 [1])	Low (since 2012 [see D1.3 Report])
Number of Bioenergy Villages	179 [1]	TBC	TBC
Number of Biogas Community Initiatives in the Country	TBC	5000 [see D1.3 Report]	TBC
Number of Biogas Plants in the Country [see D1.2 Report]	9035	185	46
Electrical Power Capacity (MWe) [see D1.2 Report]	3,543	168	146.5
Number of CHP Plants [see D1.2 Report; 2014]	20,435	611.8	177.2
Total Electricity Produced (GWh) [see D1.2 Report; 2014]	8,728	6,232	36.2
Bioenergy as a Proportion of the Total RES in the Country	12.6% [1]	1.6% [see D1.3 Report]	0.6% [see D1.2 Report]
National Financial Information			
Tariff Schemes [see D1.2 Report; 2014]	5,85-13,66 ct/kWh (Basic tariff)	FITs & RHIs (Small Scale: ≤ 250kWe)	209-230€/ MWh (Subsidy: AD Biogas ≤ 3MW)
	23,73 ct/kWh (Special tariff for small slurry plants)	FITs & RHIs (Medium Scale: 251-500kWe)	190-209€/ MWh (Subsidy: AD Biogas ≥ 3MW)
	13,38-15,26 ct/kWh (Bio-waste fermentation)	FITs & RHIs (Large Scale: 501kWe-5MWe)	114-131€/ MWh (Subsidy: Landfill, Sewage ≤ 2MW)
		FITs & RHIs (Export Tariff)	94-108€/ MWh (Subsidy: Landfill, Sewage > 2MW)
Turnover (millions €) [see D1.2 Report; 2014]	1640	485	25
National Demographic Information			
National Population (millions)	81.8 [4]	64.10	11.03
Job Opportunities Linked (Directly and Indirectly) to Biogas [see D1.2 Report; 2014]	48300	2850	150
Unemployment Rate (%)	4.7%	5.4%	25.6%
REGIONAL INFORMATION			
Region Name	Baden-Württemberg	Yorkshire & the Humber	Central and Eastern Macedonia & Thrace
Rating Biogas Readiness [*]	High	Intermediate	Low
Number of Districts or Villages Included	53	59	3
Regional Demographic Information			
Overall Regional Population (millions) [see D1.3 Report]	10.8	5.3	2.5
Unemployment Rate (%)	4.1%	6.6% [2]	24.3% [C.Macedonia: 26% (2012); E.Macedonia & Thrace: 22.5% (2012)] [3]
Number of Biogas Plants in the Region	893	13	7
Source of Community Energy	Public	Public & Private	Private
Biogas Plant Feedstock	Energy crops, wood chips, maize, other	39,500 tn manure or slurry 114,500 tn crops 127,000 tn food waste 500 tn crop waste 20,000 tn of other waste	Most biogas plants in Greece are landfill and sewage treatment plants. The rest of them use manure, slaughter house wastes, cheese dairy wastes and a small share of maize.
[*] A simple rating system for the relative biogas readiness is developed by the ISABEL INSEAD team. This rating system aims to describe the rate (high, intermediate, low) at which each regional community is prepared or willing to implement biogas incentives. The biogas readiness actually depends upon a number of interconnected factors, which may relate to policies, governmental, investor needs, social, technical and other requirements. The three selected regions for analysis by ISABEL are stated below.			
References			
[1]: http://www.wege-zum-bioenergie-dorf.de/index.php?id=2116&GID=0&kategorie1=1&kategorie2=1&kategorie3=1			
[2]: http://www.yorkshirepost.co.uk/news/uk-unemployment-rate-falls-but-yorkshire-figures-on-the-rise-1-7257926			
[3]: http://observatory.egnatia.gr/factsheets/fs_2013/SET05_factsheet_2013_en.pdf			
[4]: https://www.destatis.de/EN/FactsFigures/SocietyState/Population/Population.html			

This table presents a summary of the targeted regional characteristics.

As the project is ongoing more extensive information may be added in future reports.

3.5 Strengths and Weaknesses of the Region-Specific Communities

The key strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (SWOT) of the analysed bioenergy initiatives in the three targeted regions are given below. Each region's SWOT table was developed using information provided by the ISABEL partners who carried out the region specific interviews (presented in D1.3).

Baden-Württemberg bioenergy region in Germany

<p><u>STRENGTHS</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong civil society - High level of knowhow - Many existing biogas plants - Relatively wealthy population - Long history of cooperation (between NGOs, SMEs, communities, administration) 	<p><u>WEAKNESSES</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biogas plants are far from villages
<p><u>OPPORTUNITIES</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cooperation options with industry - Still a high potential for waste and residues - Existing plants are looking for future perspectives 	<p><u>THREATS</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cheap fossil fuels - Changes in policy (new restrictions) - Focus on other renewables

Yorkshire and the Humber region in the UK

<p><u>STRENGTHS</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Very successful examples of social entrepreneurship (SE), in sectors such as housing, forestry and assistance to disadvantaged sectors. - Awareness of the value of social entrepreneurship (SE), and the advantages of community projects - Desire to develop community funding. - Core group of actors, who are very experienced in AD, especially at a micro and small scale (hub of expertise assisting the interested communities). - Very strong emphasis on small scale AD as the less risky and most feasible option for community projects. 	<p><u>WEAKNESSES</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Small-scale demonstration plants are difficult to fund. - Large-scale AD plants, commercially driven and developed, with no direct benefits (e.g. heat district) or involvement towards the community. - It is difficult to engage with the existing group of expertise. - There is need for newly developed projects under new conditions.
<p><u>OPPORTUNITIES</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transition communities are new. - Well-executed "role models" offering innovation pilot studies (raising awareness and confidence). - Eco-villages design and development being discussed, integrated with a social entrepreneurship (SE) business model. - Local business communities are beginning to promote community energy as an investment vehicle. 	<p><u>THREATS</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of tangible assistance, which minimizes engagement. - Access to funds available for pilot innovation projects. - Access to technology of desired scale - Difficulties to coordinate with many stakeholders: community groups, housing and eco-villages, schools and universities, ethical finance, waste collection, local authorities, training and employment.

Central and Eastern Macedonia & Thrace region in Greece

<p><u>STRENGTHS</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gradual social awareness on biogas benefits - The size of the agricultural sector (huge potential amount of input material) - Highly developed agricultural sector in the region (the largest agricultural and animal breeding activities in Greece). - The area can provide a large and consistent provision of biomass. 	<p><u>WEAKNESSES</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of extending public awareness - Huge bureaucracy (social, economic, technical, policy related, other) - Relatively small livestock farms (handle manure without problems) - Negative Financial and regulatory environment - Low availability of energy corps - Supply chain issues (waste management practices securing the constant raw material flow) - Manure that could be an important source of raw material for a biogas plant in the area is mainly used as a fertilizer.
<p><u>OPPORTUNITIES</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Untapped biomass potential from the fruit processing industry. - Energy partnerships are promoted through forthcoming RES legislation (motives for entering into partnerships e.g. better tariffs and simpler licensing procedures). - Strict enforcement of the national organic waste disposable legislation. - The New National Solid Waste Management Strategy. - Pursuit for new professional activities between young unemployed people (more educated young people could act as “early adopters” for the community biogas concept by actively participating in the first projects). - The engagement and participation of local groups of stakeholders such as: local biomass producers, engineers, consultants, service providers, local authorities. - Normalization political situation in Greece, potential financial support of energy market. 	<p><u>THREATS</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unstable regional and national financial and regulatory environment. - Fears relating to future sustainability of political and financial environment. - High bureaucracy and complexity of biogas projects. - Low-to-medium level of awareness around biogas. - Negative reactions from local citizens on the installation of biogas plants. - Difficulty in the cooperation of local actors. - Reduction of feedstock supply (financial difficulties for farmers and breeders to operate properly)

Identified region-specific additional opportunities for bioenergy projects

Engaging regional stakeholders in bioenergy social franchising projects is of great importance in these projects. ISABEL's local partners thus have contributed in highlighting some key additional opportunities that can stimulate the growth of the biogas regional environments.

Germany: Baden-Württemberg

- Still a high potential for waste and residues
- Existing plants are looking for future perspectives
- Cooperation options with industry

United Kingdom: Yorkshire and the Humber

- Transition communities are new to the concept of Biogas, therefore not influenced by negative experienced
- Well executed demonstration projects, could positively influence public acceptance. They will be as innovation pilots, increasing awareness and confidence.
- Eco-villages design and development being discussed, integrated with a SE business model.
- Local business communities are beginning to promote community energy as an investment vehicle.
- Promote a different evaluation framework for community biogas initiatives, which includes impacts on social cohesion, production of “relational goods”, increased energy and food autonomy, etc.
- Comprehensive feasibility studies, co-produced with the communities, which result in robust and innovative business model.
- CESCO: Community Energy Service Company - business models around the provision of services, not just sale of products.
- Innovative ways of rising finance for initial investment, including ethical finance and crowd funding, which could value and promote the social benefits of community biogas initiatives mentioned above.
- Helping the communities going through the initial design and planning phases, reducing risk and project complexity through the adoption of simple and accurate pre-feasibility tools, and the creation of a hub of expertise. Mapping tools to evaluate the potential of wastes available in the area could be included.
- Peer to peer energy, or in general direct sale of energy to the consumer.
- Innovative use of biogas: heating greenhouses, fuel local transport, demand-driven production to compensate fluctuations in PV and wind in localised smart-grids
- Focus on consumer – the consumer is also engaged with the production, and therefore has a voice on how the community biogas initiative is run, how the profits are shared, etc.
- Need to develop the technology at the right scale, size and complexity for community projects. An open innovation platform could lead to a rapid development of the technology adapted to community biogas projects.
- Design globally and manufacture/assemble locally.
- Network of innovation pilot projects, enhancing knowledge sharing and multi-stakeholder cooperation.
- Create a sense of wonder: businesses and homes are more likely to use renewable energy if people feel emotionally connected to the source.

Greece: Central and Eastern Macedonia & Thrace

- Energy partnerships are promoted through forthcoming RES legislation (motives for entering into partnerships e.g. better tariffs and simpler licensing procedures)
- Strict enforcement of the national organic waste disposable legislation
- The New National Solid Waste Management Strategy
- Untapped biomass potential from the fruit processing industry
- Pursuit for new professional activities between young unemployed people (educated young people could act as “early adopters” for the community biogas concept by actively participating in the first projects)
- The engagement and participation of local groups of stakeholders such as: local biomass producers, engineers / consultants / service providers, local authorities

3.6 Region-Specific Facilitators for Future Biogas Community Projects

Further to the deliverable D1.3, which focuses on the “Communities’ and stakeholders’ perceptions on biogas and its implications”, the main indicators/ factors identified towards the success of a bioenergy project can be summarized in specific project aspects:

- **Sustainability aspects**
- **Technical aspects**
- **Social / community related aspects**
- **Financial aspects**
- **Governance aspects**

More specific facilitators of the analysed bioenergy projects are the following.

German regional project (Baden-Württemberg)

The German regional project (Baden-Württemberg) appears to be pioneering the bioenergy village developments across Europe. The main project facilitators identified are presented below.

Sustainability aspects

- Sustainability aspects of biogas projects

Technical aspects

- Technical knowhow and maturity of local communities regarding biogas and community biogas

Social / community related aspects

- Awareness of the added value that a community biogas project offers to the region
- Knowledge and awareness

Remarkably, the awareness that local contribution in the bioenergy sector can significantly benefit local and regional business profitability is one of the most important aspects towards the successful initiation and implementation of such projects.

Financial aspects

- Income opportunities and value generation are vital for the development of rural areas

Governance aspects

- Legislations facilitating biogas project development

UK regional project (Yorkshire and the Humber)

In the UK regional project (Yorkshire and the Humber), the main facilitators identified are the following (for more see D1.3).

Sustainability and Technical aspects

- Innovative use of digestate by adopting a new technologically produced intensive soil-less agriculture (e.g. hydroponics)

Social / community related aspects

- Demonstration of “role model” projects and best practice examples on biogas and community
- Creating new jobs and adding value for the local communities
- Awareness raising by showcasing the benefits and the social impact of the community biogas as well as by offering evidence of best practice examples
- Actively connecting projects and experts with the specific communities

Financial aspects

- Local circular economies, enabling the emergence of local businesses
- Community energy ownership can influence decision making and investments as well as smaller participatory and local scale of operations

Governance aspects

- Supportive policy developments

Greek regional project (Central and Eastern Macedonia & Thrace)

In the Greek regional project (Central and Eastern Macedonia & Thrace), seven main facilitators identified are as follows (for more see D1.3).

Sustainability and Technical aspects

- Agricultural sector
 - Focusing on the size (i.e. number of farms and livestock)
 - Untapped biomass potential from the fruit processing industry

Social / community related aspects

- Involvement of local Authorities to influence acceptance and participation to a local biogas community project
- Awareness raising through showcasing the benefits and the social impact: Pursuit for new professional activities between young unemployed people

Financial aspects

- Cooperation models and energy partnerships that will probably be promoted through the forthcoming new RES legislation

Governance aspects

- Legislations
 - New National Solid Waste Management Strategy obligating the Greek municipalities to install and use organic waste collection bins.
 - Reinforcing of organic waste disposing

3.7 Identified Region-Specific Barriers

This section presents barriers that could act detrimentally towards the successful implementation of a bioenergy project. These specific barriers have been stated by the ISABEL D1.3 partners who conducted region specific interviews. For more please refer to D1.3.

German regional project (Baden-Württemberg)

Financial aspects

- Low return on investment in biogas as compared to other renewable energy sources
- Competitive market: Price for fossil oil is very low and this trend is projected to last for a longer period

Governance aspects

- Regulatory issues regarding waste utilization, can restrict the possibilities of participation in community biogas projects
- Uncertainty regarding the continuity of financial incentives

UK regional project (Yorkshire and the Humber)

Technical aspects

- Lack of technical readiness especially in cases of small-scale enterprises
 - Biogas plants are very expensive to build

Financial aspects

- Financial risks due to lack of guaranteed feedstock for many years
- Increased uncertainty due to the recent changes at the level of the feed-in-tariffs that seem to be too low to support a viable business mode
- Lack of incentives to motivate the communities to engage in the collection of waste and to increase the recycling rate
- Minimized access to appropriate funding sources

Governance aspects

- Complex regulatory frameworks and indirect promotion of competing energy sources
 - High complexity of the biogas projects (planning, regulation, due diligence)
- Biogas projects are more complex than other renewable energy projects. Due diligence could require several supply agreements for equipment, feedstock providers, electricity supplier, etc.

Greek regional project (Central and Eastern Macedonia & Thrace)

Sustainability aspects

- Low availability of energy corps

Social / community related aspects

- The utilization of by-products (e.g. compost, heat) is uncertain as the Greek farmers are not aware of compost's advantageous properties and have a negative attitude towards compost
- The local communities' moderate-to-low overall level of understanding of and awareness around biogas

Financial aspects

- Financial crisis that has seriously affected the capability of financial institutions to fund new investments

Governance aspects

- Unstable financial and regulatory environment creating uncertainty of investments
- Bureaucracy creating complexities and discouraging local stakeholders in engaging with biogas initiatives

Overall, based on ISABEL's D1.3 results and D1.1 literature review, it has been shown that financial uncertainty, lack of assurance⁵⁴, conflict of economic interests (e.g. between former fossil oil suppliers and potential biomass providers⁵⁵), disinformation or negative propaganda can be suggested, to increase doubts amongst the community. That is regarding the cost efficiency of the plan, the security of the energy supply, the smell and noise as well as finally the potential risk of accidents. Additionally, impeding factors for the successful implementation⁵⁶ of this community bioenergy projects have been identified to relate with the lack of effective support from intermediaries, a relative paucity of support from policymakers⁵⁷ and the lack of understanding from the policy sector (who usually understand social innovations as a "one-size-fits-all" procedure⁵⁸). A lack of the following factors could have detrimental effects on the successful implementation of social innovation community energy projects.

- Local acceptance for change
- Awareness of environmental issues (in connection to the specific location of interest)
- Skills and resources
- Mutual support (issues of policy-making, place, practice, product, relating to the industries, intermediaries, individuals)
- Clarity in addressing the community responsibility

Based on the on-line carried out in April-May 2016 under ISABEL to grasp the stakeholders' perception on biogas in the 3 targeted regions, if we want to increase the willingness to join community biogas projects we need to emphasize the contribution to the environment and the increased involvement in the local communities that such projects offer and not on financial personal motives (saving from bills, making investment profits). Respondents who believe stronger in the usefulness of such a project have an increased intention to join. Thus, ISABEL needs to explicitly focus on demonstrating the usefulness of community biogas and not as much on convincing respondents on the feasibility and sustainability of these projects. Finally, respondents who are dissatisfied with the current energy market appear more eager to join community projects.

Moreover, the survey revealed that expertise (knowledge and experience) was not significantly shaping the willingness to join, while financial/economic barriers were surprisingly not affecting the willingness to join either. Respondents who did believe that economic barriers are significant belonged to groups that were very willing to join community projects. Finally, biogas perceptions (importance and overall attitude) were not significant drivers, signalling that the assumed misconceptions about biogas (e.g. smell) were not influential in the intention of respondents to join.

⁵⁴ <http://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/4/2/244/htm>

⁵⁵ <http://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/4/2/244/htm>

⁵⁶ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/integration/research/newsalert/pdf/IR10_en.pdf

⁵⁷ <http://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/4/2/244/htm>

⁵⁸ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/integration/research/newsalert/pdf/IR10_en.pdf

3.8 Conclusion of the 3-Target Region Analysis: Indicators for Successful Future Biogas Projects

Key factors for the future success of a bioenergy project are based on **communication, acceptance (a key factor) and participation**. These factors may vary considerably across the ISABEL EU regions according to their existing and prospective capacities. They are effectively also based on technical, social, economic and legislation-related factors. The consequence of the successful implementation of these factors is summarized through **active public engagement and increased investments**. Projects may be initiated from top-down initiatives, such as in cases of Germany and the UK as well as bottom-up, such as in Greece.

- **Defining Community bioenergy can influence the process of the project development**

Analysing methods that can trigger community bioenergy projects has revealed that the success of a project relates greatly to the definition of **community participation and involvement in the biogas initiative with a specific anticipated outcome**. Therefore, we proceed with the analysis of the following open question.

How can a “community” bioenergy be defined?

In exploring the success factors that can direct a bioenergy project towards a successful outcome, it has become apparent that the most crucial element of each project is the identification of the specific definition of a “community”. Although the term “community energy” has become relatively mainstream, it has become increasingly a daunting task to approach a clear and concise definition. It may be attached to a project, to an initiative, to a policy and may be related to wider issues of governance⁵⁹. Walter and Devine-Wright (2008)⁶⁰ actually revealed this issue and aimed to identify key interpretations of this term. In analysis the responses of a cohort of 12 governmental, non-governmental and industry-led initiatives, they identified that the rationale between each interpretation may actually change the interpretation of each project. Thus, such a revelation may have a considerable impact on the type of social innovations identified for each project. More specifically, Walter and Devine-Wright (2008)⁶¹ identified that “community renewable energy” may include,

- A charitable status
- Public engagement in projects physically owned by specific community members
- Local investments which empower community members to become shareholders of their local project (introducing “cooperation shares”)

All the above as well as many more definitions, may relate to numerous ideological stances about the dimension and procedures of every project. Thus each community energy project can be conceived differently.

In ISABEL all community bioenergy projects are understood either as projects whereby the energy is produced through top-down approach and thereafter distributed within communities or a bottom-up approach whereby communities can develop their own bioenergy.

⁵⁹ <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301421507004739>

⁶⁰ <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301421507004739>

⁶¹ <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301421507004739>

- **Technical knowhow, “role models” and stakeholders**

An important factor towards the success of a biogas project is the provision of appropriate (i) **technical knowhow**, (ii) **examples of successful projects that can be followed as “role models”**, as well as (iii) **information on the beneficial effects of a bioenergy project** (e.g. energy self-sufficiency and ownership). It is important that its **initiators are trusted** and considered widely as “well-known” community members and that enough **time** is provided for multiple stakeholders to engage. Specific practices, which can empower the success of a project is also **the combination of support from a large variety of stakeholders** such as, municipalities, local councils, authorities, district administrations, the mayor cooperatives, renewable energy organizations (e.g. the German Biogas Association), planning offices, funding bodies and individuals’ (e.g. inhabitants who engaged actively).

- **Methods of attracting social responses**

Apart from practical methods for implementing bioenergy projects, community energy initiatives rely also on a number of other technological methods to attract quick and effective social responses. These methods empower people to engage with these initiatives. These methods often relate to applications of **social media, social gaming, the involvement of citizens in science and communication through online platforms**. More specifically, *social media* offer important facilitators and virtual hubs for information, communication between stakeholders, social engagement, entrepreneurship and social innovation in community energy within and across borders or geographies. *Online social gaming* can educate people on environmental issues, such as waste management, conservation of biodiversity and the mitigation of natural disaster. *Communications between citizens and/or communities* that face common problems across different geographies can enable farmers and the general public to inform each other on, e.g. plant pesticides, pathogens and more, in order to promote a more ecological agriculture. **Local networking and face-to-face communications** has been proved in all three targeted areas to address and highlight the reasons for the implementation of the project (stating the “common good”). Through communication, information can be made available and transparently (through communication) can be achieved across the community members. Thereafter, they show trust in the bioenergy projects. This information may include **data on the local financial and economic benefits** of the alternative energy project implementation. The best practices however, relate also to a softer **social engagement in this project through local events** (e.g. on topics of alternative energy production, use, benefits), **school presentations, exhibitions, workshops and press releases**. In such events, local core competencies can be presented in simple ways to the local communities and cost benefits from merging or acquiring a new alternative energy sources for biogas (as compared to the use of, e.g. fossil fuels) can be revealed.

- **Increasing willingness for behavioural change**

The analysis of important attributes of social innovation in community energy practices suggests that the socio-economic motives for such projects can be stronger than the environmental ones. **Successful social innovations applied to community energy projects create alternative marketplaces that trigger consumer behavioural changes**. This can be by following a number of methods and utilising various tools (such as social media, and social gaming). Behavioural changes can also be triggered through **cooperatives** (playing a direct role in profit generation and sharing) and **energy ownership, shared-resources and micro-franchising**.⁶² The provision of **inclusive sourcing** (that engages small farming companies in larger corporations) can also contribute towards the creation of new market connections, increase farmer learning and benefit the large corporations’ legitimacy in local markets by enabling branding of their products as “ethical”⁶³. Financial innovations are strongly related to social and community energy

⁶² Ibid ³

⁶³ Clinton, L. & Whisnant, R. (2014), *Model Behavior: 20 Business Model Innovations for Sustainability*, SustainAbility Ltd. (www.sustainability.com)

innovations and can translate in crowd funding approaches to alternative ideas and thus attract investments for community energy purposes.

- **Motivation mix: important preconditions for the success of a project**

Based on the analysis of ISABEL's qualitative research, as well as its literature review presented in D1.1, it has been identified that *important preconditions*⁶⁴ for the beginning of a social innovation community energy projects relate to the **motivation mix of the community**. This means that there is wide variety of motives that lead a community in succeeding towards a new incentive scheme. There are effectively three types of motivation and they target **environmental and ecological motives** (related to eco-friendly, sensible uses of natural resources), **social and anthropocentric motives** as well as **economic motives**. Interestingly, although the environmental motives should be considered as more important (given the environmental value of using renewable energy sources), it is necessary to acknowledge that economic motives appeared to be very strong. The latter relate mostly to the potential of bioenergy independence of the community and consequently the potential of a reduction of individuals' and the community's energy bills.

- **Policy framework and public acceptance**

Energy partnerships can be promoted through forthcoming renewable energy legislations (see all D1.3 Report). According to the input provided by the Greek regional partners for the future perspectives for biogas, it has been shown that governmental policies can be regarded as rather positive. This becomes obvious when considering the facilitators and barriers that have been reported for the region in the frame of D1.3. The Greek Ministry of Environment and Energy, for example, has included the promotion of energy partnerships in its forthcoming policy measures. Energy partnerships are expected to be funded under the new act and to be regulated with a **dedicated legal framework that will offer financial motives for entering into partnerships**. These motives apply in all cases, whether Germany, UK or Greece and target **better tariffs** (e.g. in Germany), **FITs and RHIs** (e.g. export tariffs in the UK), **tax reliefs and subsidies** (e.g. in Greece) **as well as simpler licensing procedures** (see also table in paragraph 2.2). The concept of energy partnerships holds the potential to overcome the most important barriers for the development of biogas in Greece. Therefore, (i) **new legislation about disposable organic waste** (i) **new national solid waste management strategies** and more incentive schemes can be of particular value.

⁶⁴ <http://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/4/2/244/htm>

4. Enhancing Biogas Communities: Ideas, Methods and Tools

Social innovation illustration (source⁶⁵)

Comparing alternative markets in Europe as well as focusing in their environmental, technical, social, community related, financial and governance aspects, has shown that predictor of growth in the sector of biogas are influenced by the combination of all factors. However, In the case of **top-bottom developments**, it would seem that **legal and financial motives** offer the most important factors for the initiation of bioenergy projects. For example, in Sweden and Germany, which are two of the most successful nations in terms of renewable energy project development that subsidies and tax reliefs appeared to be the most important incentives for biomass project developments ⁶⁶. Regulating competition also across the renewable energy sectors is also important for individual stakeholder decision-making towards biogas.

In **bottom-up developments**, it would seem that initiatives depend mostly on awareness raising strategies. **Communication** increases trust and active engagement in projects that target a “common good”. Remarkably, research by Fors (2009) ⁶⁷ has shown that **public awareness of the benefits of the use of biogas can be equally important to financial motives**. It suggests additionally that the availability of appropriate technology for bioenergy production cannot offer enough of an incentive to attract investment for a community bioenergy project.

Analysing bioenergy projects, across ISABEL’s targeted regions and Europe in general (as presented in D1.1 “Social Innovation and Community Energy best practices, methods and tools across Europe”), has shown that improving and enhancement of both **top-bottom** and/ or **bottom-up** existing and future successful bioenergy communities depend on the following relation,

$$\text{Communication + Motives} = \text{Cooperation (Partnerships) + Investments}$$

In order to adopt and defuse community biogas projects, this paragraph will present recommendations through which the likelihood of such projects being successful could increase. These recommendations are **effective social innovations that can promote and strengthen community biogas projects**.

⁶⁵http://youngfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/04/YOFJ2785_Tepsie_A-guide_for_researchers_06.01.15_WEB.pdf

⁶⁶ Fors, P.-M. (2009). *The German, Swedish and UK wood based bio energy markets from an investment perspective*. Uppsala, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences: Faculty of Forest Sciences.

⁶⁷ Fors, P.-M. (2009). *The German, Swedish and UK wood based bio energy markets from an investment perspective*. Uppsala, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences: Faculty of Forest Sciences.

4.1 Social innovation Adoption and Diffusion Models

In the following table, we present a **typology of social innovation and forms of growth**.⁶⁸ This shows the method by which growth is conceptualized, through different forms of social innovation. Adopting in new social ventures and enterprise requires following a process of “scaling” and “scaling up” a project’s value and impact. Creating new legislation can be conceptualized through policy diffusions. Achieving a behavioural change can be enhanced through the diffusion of the social innovation strategies, which can thereafter be followed by successful project systemic change.

Form of social innovation	Conceptualizing growth
New social enterprise/venture	Scaling; scaling up
New legislation	Policy diffusion
New behavior: Individual led e.g. recycling	Diffusion; behavior change
New service: Organization led e.g. personalized budgets	Organizational diffusion & Systemic change

Figure 13. Processes of social innovation⁶⁹

The literature review and ISABEL’s research have shown that **social innovation projects develop relatively sequentially across their lifespan**. This sequence can be described⁷⁰ as follows and is designed based on our currently understanding of the essential elements of a successful community energy project.

Figure 14. Sequential approach to social innovation

⁶⁸http://youngfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/11/Davies-Simon_Growing-social-innovation_ISIRC-2013.pdf

⁶⁹<http://youngfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2012/10/How-to-innovate-the-tools-for-social-innovation.pdf> & cohousing.org.uk

⁷⁰http://youngfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/11/Davies-Simon_Growing-social-innovation_ISIRC-2013.pdf

As all projects that aim to achieve a social impact may include numerous elements that are non-replicable, we have explored **different typologies of social enterprise as well as their structures and definitions**.⁷¹ This is to categorize the type of challenge faced in each project and thereafter propose an overarching model or context in which community bioenergy projects may be related. Analysing the literature and especially in studying the pioneering work, beginning in the 1960s by John Durand⁷², Jack Dalton⁷³ and Muhammad Yunus⁷⁴. Their work focuses on social enterprises and fuels the growing quest towards sustainability across sectors and organizational types. The purpose of the typologies that will be presented through schematic drawings below is to (i) **analyse** the rich mosaic of the different operational models across enterprises (e.g. cooperation between different stakeholders) and thereafter to (ii) **inspire** innovative approaches towards the creation of sustainable community energy futures.

In aiming to achieve the most effective positive impact on community biogas projects, the following operation models have been explored and are presented below. These illustrations can be used to create a social (measurable impact) and economic value (income), as well as to influence and enhance institutional, programs, or service operations.

Entrepreneurial support model⁷⁵

In this model a social enterprise provides business support and financial services to clients⁷⁶ or self-employed populations who can thereafter sell their own products or services in the open market.

Figure 15. Entrepreneurial support model

Image source⁷⁷

Market Intermediary model⁷⁸

In this model, market intermediaries provide services to individuals, firms or cooperatives and help them access their market.

Figure 16. Market Intermediary model

Image source⁷⁹

⁷¹http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial+Enterprise+Typology+Updated+Novem.pdf

⁷² <http://www.mdi.org>

⁷³ <http://www.pioneerhumanserv.com>

⁷⁴ <http://grameen-info.org>

⁷⁵http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial+Enterprise+Typology+Updated+Novem.pdf

⁷⁶ <http://www.approtec.org>

⁷⁷http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial+Enterprise+Typology+Updated+Novem.pdf

⁷⁸http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial+Enterprise+Typology+Updated+Novem.pdf

Employment model⁸⁰

In this model, social enterprises create the appropriate employment environment; provide training and jobs to particular member of the society, such as, homeless, at risk-youth and ex-offenders⁸¹.

Figure 17. Employment model

Image source⁸²

Fee-for-service model⁸³

This model of sells services directly to the individuals, firms, communities, or to a third parties.

Figure 18. Fee-for-service model

Image source⁸⁴

Cooperative model⁸⁵

This model seems to be closer to the types of models that have been analyzed by ISABEL. The cooperative model provides direct benefits to its cooperative members. That is through market information, technical assistance, collective bargaining power, economies of bulk purchase, access to external markets and more. The cooperative membership relates mostly to small-scale producers (e.g. farmers) or to communities that have a common need. These cooperative memberships benefit directly from their community project by increasing income, receiving employment and more.

Figure 19. Cooperative model

Image source⁸⁶

⁷⁹http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial+Enterprise+Typology+Updated+Novem.pdf

⁸⁰http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial+Enterprise+Typology+Updated+Novem.pdf

⁸¹ <http://www.digitaldividedata.org>

⁸²http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial+Enterprise+Typology+Updated+Novem.pdf

⁸³http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial+Enterprise+Typology+Updated+Novem.pdf

⁸⁴http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial+Enterprise+Typology+Updated+Novem.pdf

⁸⁵http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial+Enterprise+Typology+Updated+Novem.pdf

Market linkage model⁸⁷

In this model, market linkages are drawn between local firms or producers and cooperatives or external markets.

Figure 20. Market linkage model
Image source⁸⁸

Service subsidizing model⁸⁹

This model sells specific services to external markets and uses the income generated to fund its social programs.

Figure 21. Service subsidizing model
Image source⁹⁰

The above are only a few models that exist currently to support projects that aim at generating value through social impact achieved. This demonstrates as well that identifying a single framework for social innovations triggering community biogas is a complex task because there is a diversity of stakeholders' involvement and expectations in such projects that aim for a social impact. The shifting stakeholders' expectations, from profit to non-profit⁹¹, from commercial to community-led, from large to small scale, suggest that our projects are **hybrid** and thus do not fall readily within one single model category. Hybrid project practitioners can be, for instance, (i) non-profit organizations with income-generating activities, (ii) social enterprises, (iii) socially responsive businesses, (iv) corporations practicing social responsibility.

More specifically, a hybrid project organization can be influenced by a number of interrelated motives (as suggested in our ISABEL D1.1 and in the project analysis of this report as well as D1.3). The goal is to

⁸⁶http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial_Enterprise_Typology_Updated_Novem.pdf

⁸⁷http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial_Enterprise_Typology_Updated_Novem.pdf

⁸⁸http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial_Enterprise_Typology_Updated_Novem.pdf

⁸⁹http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial_Enterprise_Typology_Updated_Novem.pdf

⁹⁰http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial_Enterprise_Typology_Updated_Novem.pdf

⁹¹ Reis, T. (1999) "Unleashing New Resources and Entrepreneurship for the Common Good: A Scan, Synthesis, and Scenario for Action", W.K. Kellogg Foundation

generate a socio-economic value. Reinvesting in the community biogas mission activities as well as retaining its operations is the ultimate goal for hybrid business growth, which is also the goal of community bioenergy projects.

	Purely Philanthropic	Hybrid ^{92p.14}	Purely commercial
Motives	Appeal to goodwill	Mixed motives	Appeal to self-interest
Methods	Mission-driven	Balance of mission and market	Market-driven
Goals	Social value creation	Social and economic value creation	Economic value creation
Destination of Income/Profit	Directed toward mission activities of nonprofit organization (required by law or organizational policy)	Reinvested in mission activities or operational expenses, and/or retained for business growth and development (for-profits may redistribute a portion)	Distributed to shareholders and owners

Figure 22. Hybrid organization

Image source⁹²

Literature has shown that it is a daunting task to design and develop a replicable complex project. That is because they do not seem to uniformly operate with the same stakeholders. They function as multi-unit operations and include a mix of different (i) **social programs**, (ii) **financial objectives**, (iii) **market opportunities** and (iv) **funding structures**⁹³.

Through the lens of social innovation, creating social impact and profitability expects that a sustainable equilibrium between these factors will be developed. This so-called **dual value of social and economic sustainability seems to define all social impact projects** and can be described by the image shown below.

Figure 23. Dual value of social and economic sustainability equilibrium

Image source⁹⁴

⁹²[http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial Enterprise Typology Updated Novem.pdf](http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial+Enterprise+Typology+Updated+Novem.pdf)

⁹³ Dees, G. (1998), "Enterprising Nonprofits", Harvard Business Review.

⁹⁴[http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial Enterprise Typology Updated Novem.pdf](http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/32431718/SE_typology.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1466327011&Signature=bL78DqOOTIGzNmyCrTxig%2FBZgnE%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DSocial+Enterprise+Typology+Updated+Novem.pdf)

4.2 Social Franchising Concept in Biogas

Further to the above, and as this projects aims to identify methods to approach, adopt, enhance and diffuse bioenergy initiatives, we have identified **a method to transfer new or existing information, increase knowledge and understanding as well as presenting experiences that can benefit a society**⁹⁵. This is termed **social franchising** and could be one approach towards successful replicable biogas community projects triggered by social innovation.

More specifically, although traditional franchising is described as a commercial activity, social franchising is not. **Its purpose is to stimulate people to work together and exchange ideas for a wider social goal.**⁹⁶ Providing new **job opportunities to people in need, democratizing the economy and tackling climate change**, are three main goals of social franchising.⁹⁷ Social franchising increases ownership of community projects, as it is run by members of the society as well as business partners or other stakeholders that can generate profit for the specific community. **Profitability** is essential for social franchising projects, as in bioenergy projects, because without financial revenue these projects cannot survive, grow and meet the given social goal for socio-economic sustainability and reinvestments in community needs.⁹⁸ **Social franchising strategies'** specifics are non-replicable; however their principles can be replicated. These principles are summarized below.

Figure 24. Achieving Systemic Change

⁹⁵ <http://www.socialfranchising.coop/what-is-social-franchising>

⁹⁶ <http://www.socialfranchising.coop/what-is-social-franchising>

⁹⁷ <http://www.socialfranchising.coop/what-is-social-franchising>

⁹⁸ <http://www.socialfranchising.coop/what-is-social-franchising>

In the case of community biogas projects, social franchising networks can carry out through social innovations. These innovations however would need to focus in three steps,

1. **Adoption to the social impact project characteristics**
2. **Promotion of social behavioural change**
 - a. **Following simple awareness and acceptance raising techniques**
3. **Growth and diffusion of social innovation project**

Further to the analysis of the characteristics of social innovation projects as well as the challenges and structure of biogas and renewable energy projects, we believe that the above is a viable structure (though more models and structures could be identified and analysed in the future).

Social Innovation Step 1: Adoption to the social impact project characteristics

Based on our research and understanding of the success factors for social innovation to trigger biogas projects, the following diagram illustrates the method in which a bioenergy projects with an anticipated social impact can be initiated and developed. More specifically, this diagram shows that the first action towards the successful initiation of a biogas community project is to offer **prompts** (e.g. information, triggers, inspiration) and thus conceptualize the given project to the community that could benefit from it as well as get involved in it. The second action is to **disseminate** useful information and thus raise awareness, trust and attract social engagement. The third action is to **manage the biogas resources** in terms mostly of its technical infrastructure and capabilities. This can then lead to the adoption and initiation of the first projects tests and trials.

Further to the three first actions that are required to be taken prior to the actual initiation of the project in-practice, a coordination team can be attracted or involved according to the level of control that is expected to be taken over the innovation process. This can be regulated according to regional needs and their biogas “readiness” (maturity). Thereafter, the fourth action towards the initiation and adoption of the biogas project, formal stakeholder relations should be established. That could be between social enterprises, governments, municipalities or authorities, experts, cooperatives and more. This kind of formal project relations established is stated as **affiliation**.

Successful tests and trials as well as coordination can finally attract **finances** to the given social/sustainability venture through action 5, which aims are **venture financing, investor engagement, crowd funding** or more.

All actions described above are summarised in the following diagram. This schematic diagram has been designed based on information from the D1.1, D1.2 and D1.3 deliverables as well as other sources.^{99,100}

⁹⁹ <http://fr.slideshare.net/sixslides/generating-social-innovation-tools-techniques-and-methods>

¹⁰⁰ <http://www.socialfranchising.coop/what-is-social-franchising>

Primary action

→ Primary path

Social Innovation Step 2: Amplifying social innovations methods and promoting social behaviour change

A general method to create sustainable biogas communities is to identify the appropriate conditions for social innovation, reveal the district processes for developing sustainable initiatives and target a natural way to promote the transformation of an existing system into another one.

Further to this, the adoption of a social impact project and its successful initiation require the promotion of behavioural change. This relates to the second action described as **dissemination**.

Through **communication**, public acceptance can be increased and obstacles can be overcome. Such obstacles can stem from multiple sources, such as community members, local stakeholders with conflicting interests, fear of economic risks and lack of support from intermediaries as well as paucity from policymakers. During community energy projects, **community members** should increase their understanding of the methods followed to produce energy for their own community. This could mean, for example, that they would need to **connect with experts**.

Reconfiguring social behaviour cannot be achieved through a single step however. It requires a whole mechanism (an inter-connected system) that can promote the process and implementation of community biogas projects. This process is based on social innovation triggers and its system entails **preconditions**, **motives** for project initiation and **active engagement** in the creation of successful bioenergy villages.

Therefore, we have identified some simple awareness and acceptance-raising techniques

Source¹⁰¹

These techniques target the **dissemination** of project incentives and the specific pool of methods and tools that could be utilized in achieving a positive and sustainable engagement in a biogas project. Information dissemination relates to a “tree” of triggers between (i) communicating the **innovation characteristics**, through examples of “role models”, energy “champions” (see D1.1 Samsø island) and (ii) presenting the

¹⁰¹ https://www.h-brs.de/files/erklaerung_soziale_innovationen_fuerd_2_0.pdf

innovation benefits (e.g. lasting financial incentives). This can lead to the development of **social entrepreneurship** illustrating a clear direction towards the project goals.

Investing time and effort in **communicating energy challenges, local core competences and bioenergy capacities** can reveal the benefits of the proposed community energy venture through social innovation. **Raising awareness of the beneficial effects of bioenergy communities (e.g. community energy self-sufficiency, increased job opportunities, empowered re-investments) and developing a sense of social responsibility** can be achieved through, for example:

- **Local networking and face-to-face communications**
- A wide diversity of **bioenergy activities** in the successful bioenergy regions
- **Bioenergy-tours** through excursions to existing successful bioenergy projects, which act as “role-models” for future projects (see more on the idea of providing “role models” in D1.1 report)
- Bioenergy **exhibition, local information events and articles** in the press
- **Conferences and workshops**
 - Consultation workshops
 - Social innovation incubators¹⁰²
 - Biogas think-tanks

Further to the D1.1 literature review as well as to responses provided in D1.3, it is expected that community bioenergy is the result of the joint venture between multiple **social innovation animators**. These are defined as individuals or groups who have a high interest in community biogas. These are the one that will lead the way for the co-creation of the regional biogas through the use of social innovation methods and could be, for instance:

- Individuals or groups of stakeholders
- Governmental agents
- Expert groups
- Universities and schools
- Private investors
- Press releases
- Crowdsourcing
- NGOs

Additionally, the use of ICT could increase participation, awareness and trust in bioenergy projects through:

- Online networks¹⁰³ and portals
- Social media
- Social gaming
- Involvement of citizens in science and communication through online platforms

Successful methods to raise awareness and attract actively engagement as well as investments relate also to the so-called “**sweeteners**”. These can be,

- **Financial “sweeteners”** (farmers benefiting from the initiative)
- **Operational** (related to cooperation, policy provisions and subsidies)
- **Mutual stakeholder (franchisee) dependencies** can create the sense of common responsibility and a shared value¹⁰⁴
- **Presentation of a motivation mix, which contributes to an evolution of social responsibility and behavioural change**¹⁰⁵

¹⁰² <http://fr.slideshare.net/sixslides/generating-social-innovation-tools-techniques-and-methods>

¹⁰³ http://youngfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/04/YOFJ2785_Tepsie_A-guide_for_researchers_06.01.15_WEB.pdf

¹⁰⁴ Michelini, L. (2012), *Social Innovation and New Business Models: Creating Shared Value in Low-Income Markets*, Springer.

¹⁰⁵ Michelini, L. (2012), *Social Innovation and New Business Models: Creating Shared Value in Low-Income Markets*, Springer.

This can be environmental and ecological, social and anthropocentric as well as economic. The **active involvement of a variety of stakeholders** (which could range, for example, from municipalities, authorities and policy makers, to cooperatives, renewable energy organizations, planning offices, funding bodies and local community members) can also influence significantly the success of a community energy project. Local stakeholders' interested often are driven by **economic benefits**. Therefore, following successful and profitable **"role model"** projects may gain their local trust and attract investments.

Social Innovation Step 3: Growth and diffusion of social innovation

The final step toward of a social innovation project is its **enhancement and growth**. According to TEPSIE, social innovations are rarely static and rational.¹⁰⁶ Therefore, social innovation factors which can stimulate the pace of growth have been analysed. The TEPSIE diagram shown below illustrates a map for innovation of social purpose organizations. This has been selected as the structure is similar to that of community biogas projects adoption and scaling.

Starting small and growing large is a mantra for spreading growth through of social sustainable ventures. However, this is rarely applicable in projects that are organised by the public sector and seldom start from scratch. The diffusion of social innovation projects is a highly contested field as it relates to numerous interconnected factors, such as those of local consumer interest, technological capacities and competitive rivalries across renewable energy sectors. In aiming to identify representative methods to diffuse social innovations to trigger community biogas projects, a qualitative approach (based on interviews administered and analysed in D1.3) has been followed.

Power and interest have thus been found to be remarkably connected to social innovation diffusion. This is particularly applicable in cases whereby a national agenda, policy-makers interest and or investor interests are very closely related to a community energy initiative.

Achieving the growth and diffusion of a bioenergy project therefore relates to the process of branching system change (essentially a procedure of social franchising, see Appendix 1). Branching relates to an achieved systemic behavioural change with visible impacts on social and state related provisions (e.g. transformation of laws and regulations).

¹⁰⁶http://youngfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/04/YOFJ2785_Tepsie_A-guide_for_researchers_06.01.15_WEB.pdf

5. Region-Specific Recommendations and Forthcoming Initiatives

Further to the analysis of the “biogas landscape and specificities in the three-targeted regions” (see for details D1.2) it was emphasised that bioenergy projects vary considerably. This comes as no surprise as wide variety of biogas projects across the world are different and thus are largely **non-replicable**. Further to the results of the D1.2 and D1.3 deliverable information (for detailed information see deliverables), as well as to the ISABEL partner reports of the **strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats**, this paragraph will consider **identified existing barriers to bioenergy projects in the targeted regions** and will aim to discuss solutions. Therefore, a few simple recommendations coupled with reported (by the ISABEL partners who conducted the three-targeted regional interviews) forthcoming initiatives for the three-targeted regions analysed by ISABEL, will be presented. **It should be noted that the recommendations and forthcoming region-specific initiatives outlined below are by no means conclusive and will be analysed further in the future.**

German regional project (Baden-Württemberg)

Further to the analysis of ISABEL’s German region (targeting the “context & intervening conditions”, “causal conditions”, “approach, action and interaction strategy”, “methods & tools”, and “consequences after the implementation of the bioenergy project”, see paragraph 2.1 and D1.2-3), it has been identified that the main detrimental aspects for the **adoption and diffusion** of bioenergy initiatives in Germany are **financial and regulation-related**. However, literature review and interview analyses (by ISABEL partners) have shown that the success of bioenergy projects relies on numerous interconnected aspects. Therefore, considerations made for future strategies to develop successful regional bioenergy projects could focus on the following:

Financial aspects and issues of governance

- **Increase biogas investment returns** as compared to other renewable energy sources
- **Respond to the existing market competition:** Price for fossil fuel is currently very low and this trend is projected to be long-lasting.
 - Soften existing renewable energy market rivalries
- Present successful investment “**role-models**” to negotiate with policy-makers
- **Offering financial incentives**

Most of the existing biogas plants in Germany receive a fixed remuneration for the electricity that they produce during the first 20 years. However, so far, **no strategies exist for these plants after this period**. In order to prevent negative impacts on biogas projects additional efforts should be made to develop positive future perspectives for the plants and the associated farmers and local communities.

Technical aspects

Although, the technical solutions for residue and green waste utilization already exist, biogas in Germany is currently based on energy crops. The main obstacles for the residue and green waste utilization are economic and regulatory issues. The economic aspects are currently overruled by the EEG legislation, which offers high remuneration for electricity production. Other regulatory aspects that hinder the utilization of this input material are the strict waste management regulations. Therefore, in order to increase the sustainable solutions that are based on waste and residues, biogas projects could consider including additional social, ecological and resource efficiency aspects. In addition, biogas production should be redefined. That is by stimulating **a more intense cooperation between plant managers and communities / citizens.**

In addition, it would seem that future bioenergy initiatives should **include new techniques**. Such as, input alternative materials and various products of biogas.

- **Output biogas products** should run primarily for electricity production
 - Consider **alternative output products**, which should be tailored to the local community needs (e.g. heat, cooling, fuel)
- **Input alternative materials**, as it would seem that biogas plants cannot just target on energy production
- **Working on the existing high potential for waste and residues** as well as existing plants' future perspectives

Raising awareness and acceptance

Community acceptance is a strong enabler for any development or action in rural areas including biogas plants and participation projects in general. Low community acceptance can cause challenges and even lead to the failure of projects. In contrast, existing and emerging community biogas projects can lead to a higher acceptance of biogas itself. Several factors appear to have a positive effect on public acceptance towards community biogas projects such as the provision of information on the,

- **Number of partners** involved in the biogas project
- **Size of the biogas plants** as well as related aspects (transportation and environmental)
- **Financial gains** resulting from the communal project
- **Time to realization** of such a project appears to have a direct impact on the stakeholders' acceptance levels and decision-making

A possible way to deal with the level of complexity in developing of a *best-fit methodology* for the Baden-Württemberg regional contexts and circumstances,

- **Workshops** could provide a seamless information flow and communicate appropriate information to the local communities and all interested stakeholders.

Social / community impact based on their involvement in biogas supply and demand operations

Biogas projects could strongly benefit from the **community participation** in energy supply and demand operations, as this could lead to **higher acceptance rates and help redefine biogas as a social good**.

- **Promoting cooperation options with the biogas industry**
- **Biogas supply**
 - As **local communities and stakeholders** seem to wish to be part of a biogas project that is being developed in their region, many possibilities for **participation on different levels of the biogas project operations** (e.g. delivering input material, management, financing, consuming biogas products, decision making, etc.) could be found.
- **Biogas demand**
 - **A biogas community could be formed at the demand side**

UK regional project (Yorkshire and the Humber)

Further to the analysis of ISABEL's UK region (targeting the "context & intervening conditions", "causal conditions", "approach, action and interaction strategy", "methods & tools", and "consequences after the implementation of the bioenergy project", see paragraph 2.1 and D1.2-3), it has been identified that the main detrimental aspects for the **adoption and diffusion** of bioenergy initiatives in the UK are **technical, financial and regulation-related**. However, literature review and interview analyses (by ISABEL partners) have shown that the success of bioenergy projects relies on numerous interconnected aspects. Therefore, considerations made for future strategies to develop successful regional bioenergy projects could focus on the following:

Technical aspects

- **Stimulating technical readiness especially in cases of small-scale enterprises**
 - Biogas plants should become less expensive to build
- **Innovative use of biogas through the development of localised smart-grids**

- Developing technology (at appropriate scale, size and complexity) to function as an **open innovation platform** leading to a rapid social innovation adoption and diffusion
- **Designing a global manufacturing/assembling service**
- There is a **technical potential** available in terms of food waste and other waste
- Providing guaranteed feedstock through new use of **new alternative materials**

Financial aspects

- **Respond to the existing market competition:** Price for fossil fuel is currently very low and this trend is projected to be long-lasting.
- Housing estates could offer opportunities for **local closed-loop economic benefits**, providing employment, waste treatment, production and consumption of healthy food. In these cases, places for installing the AD system could be garages, basements, roofs, and central squares.
- **Local businesses** could promote community energy as an investment vehicle
- **Introducing ethical finance and crowd funding** strategies, which could value and promote the social benefits of community biogas initiatives mentioned above
- **Focusing on the supply chain**
 - **Offering financial incentives** to motivate the communities to engage in the collection of waste and to increase the recycling rate
 - Provide accessibility costs for **AD operators**
 - Empowering **access to professional services**, to help with the development and management of projects

Governance aspects

- **Policy and Incentives**
e.g. The competition for energy rich wastes should decrease
- **Increasing support from local councils through incentives that look beyond the energy generation**, and encompass, for example, the advantages that AD, the provision of a wider public energy income structure etc.

Raising awareness and acceptance

As the UK communities are new to the concept of biogas, well executed demonstration projects, could offer **positive influence public acceptance**.

- **Workshops** could provide a sense of “a Living-Lab” where information and “role models” could be presented to the local communities and all interested stakeholders
 - Enhancing knowledge sharing and multi-stakeholder cooperation
 - Helping the communities going through the initial design and planning phases – reducing the risk and project complexity through the adoption of simple and accurate pre-feasibility tools, and the creation of a hub of expertise
 - Effective tools to evaluate the potential of wastes available in the area could be identified and presented
- **Present comprehensive feasibility studies**, co-produced with the communities, which result in robust and innovative business model.
e.g. CESCO (Community Energy Service Company) business models which offer energy services that target issues beyond the renewable energy products sale

Attracting community participation in biogas projects/ initiatives

- Create a new customized **evaluation framework for community biogas initiatives**, which could present biogas impacts on social cohesion, production of “relational goods”, increased energy and food autonomy, etc.
- **Promoting peer-to-peer energy**, or in general direct sale of energy to the consumer
- Create a **sense of wonder**: businesses and homes are more likely to use renewable energy if people feel emotionally connected to the source

Greek regional project (Central and Eastern Macedonia & Thrace)

The special characteristic of this region is that it is located within a nation that faces a large-scale social and economic crisis. Consequently, despite the good feed-in conditions, the investor and communities refrain from starting new projects and providing financial support for biogas projects. While biogas plants exist and so does biomass and organic waste, legislations as well as public-private incentives are not strong or inexistent. **The lack of adequate “know-how”**, which by contrast is demonstrated in **Germany**, indicates that there is need to **develop cooperative international schemes whereby stakeholders will learn from successful “role models”**. The existing feedstock in the analysed region (Central and eastern Macedonia & Thrace region) offers a high potential of biogas producer nationally. With the support of public and public sector initiatives social franchising can take place in the regional community analysed.

Further to the analysis of ISABEL’s Greek region (targeting the “context & intervening conditions”, “causal conditions”, “approach, action and interaction strategy”, “methods & tools”, and “consequences after the implementation of the bioenergy project”, see paragraph 2.1 and D1.2-3), it has been identified that the detrimental aspects for the **adoption and diffusion** of bioenergy initiatives in Greece are multiple and can be summarized as **environmental** (sustainability aspects), **social, financial and regulation-related**. Therefore, considerations made for future strategies to develop successful regional bioenergy projects could focus in the following.

Sustainability / Technical aspects

- **Regulating the availability of energy corps**
e.g. by providing guaranteed feedstock through new use of **new alternative materials**
- **Developing and using by-products, such as compost**
- Diverging the biomass potential from the fruit processing industry

Financial aspects

- **Familiarizing local stakeholders with biogas and related financial benefits**
 - Familiarizing local stakeholders with the financial aspects of a biogas projects
 - Proposing successful business model that take into account the regional specificities

Governance aspects

- **Energy partnerships can be promoted through forthcoming renewable energy legislation** (incentives for entering into partnerships e.g. better tariffs and simpler licensing procedures)
- **In the near future (1-5 years) biogas plants are approved for construction**
 - Two different licensing procedures are being developed, for biogas plants > 1 MW or < 1 MW. However, in both cases, the potential investors should represent a “mature” AD development. That is through presenting:
 - Construction License from the Urban Planning Authority
 - Installation License from the Prefecture’s Development Department or payment for a connection contract with the grid operator
- New **National Solid Waste Management Strategy** is being developed obliging the Greek municipalities to install and use organic waste collection bins. This will result in developing substantial quantities of organic waste (at the possession of Greek Municipalities) that will require some kind of treatment, with biogas plants being an interesting option
 - Local authorities could offer guidance, coordination and administrative support

The new legislation introduces a new electricity market model, which is expected to be completed by the end of 2017. The aim is to gradually increase the **participation and commitment** in the electricity market from the new renewable energy stations, as well as monitoring of the weighted cost of electricity production to avoid unnecessary financing of the selling to the grid rate. The Greek state intends to adopt a scheme, starting from the 1st of January of 2017, for awarding financing through a competitive bidding

process. The rate financing will be such so as the IRR is 9-10%. **The National Target for biogas penetration, presented in the following table:**

	Ratio of installed capacity			
	Renewable energy target		Actual renewable energy	
	2014	2020	2014	2015
Hydropower plants	3700	4650	3273	3277
Small (0 - 15 MW)	300	350	220	224
Large (> 15MW)	3400	4300	3053	3053
Photovoltaic plants	1500	2200	2435	2443
(+solar roof tiles)				
Other installations	1000	1450	N/A	N/A
Heliothermic plants	120	250	0	0
Wind farms	4000	7500	1662	1772
Biomass, Biogas	200	350	47	51

Information presented in the table above was provided by ISABEL partners in Greece.

Social / community related aspects

- **Promoting the engagement and participation of local groups of stakeholders** such as: local biomass producers, engineers / consultants / service providers, local authorities
- **Connecting local stakeholders with their counterparts abroad** in order to exchange good practices, to transfer know-how and to share experiences
- **Developing partnerships to support community energy**
Working together with public, private and third sector partners can be an effective way for communities to achieve their objectives. It can bring together the right mix of skills, experience, assets, finance and investment with local interests and engaged communities.

Raising awareness and acceptance

- **Developing job opportunities to engage young people currently unemployed** (more educated young people could act as “early adopters” for the community biogas concept by actively participating in the first projects)
- **Providing access to reliable and relevant information and advice**
e.g. this could include the development of a ‘One-Stop Shop’ information resource for community energy groups and their partners. A range of services and resources thereafter could be made available in order to promote the development of community bioenergy projects.

Raising awareness of the beneficial effects of bioenergy communities (e.g. community energy self-sufficiency, increased job opportunities, empowered re-investments) and developing a sense of social responsibility could be achieved also through a number of steps and events such as,

- **Local networking and face-to-face communications**
- A wide diversity of **bioenergy activities** in the successful bioenergy regions
- **Bioenergy-tours** through excursions to existing successful bioenergy projects, which act as “role-models” for future projects (see more on the idea of providing “role models” in D1.1 report)
- Bioenergy **exhibition, local information events and articles** in the press
- **Conferences and workshops**
 - Consultation workshops
 - Social innovation incubators¹⁰⁷
 - Biogas think-tanks

¹⁰⁷ <http://fr.slideshare.net/sixslides/generating-social-innovation-tools-techniques-and-methods>

6. Conclusions

In this report, we have analysed three regions in Europe, which represent a ranging *maturity* in *biogas readiness*¹⁰⁸ from *mature, to intermediate and preliminary*. Each region thus represents a different condition in terms of its,

- Technical knowhow, “role models” and stakeholders engagement
- Methods of attracting social responses and Increasing willingness for behavioural change
- Motivation mix (environmental and ecological motives, social and anthropocentric motives as well as economic)
- Policy framework and public acceptance

Baden-Württemberg is ISABEL’s *mature in biogas* region analysed. It is one of the four most successful bioenergy villages in Europe. **Germany** has pioneered the development of bioenergy villages since the 1990s and has developed 179 bioenergy villages to date. It has the lowest unemployment rate in Europe and has incentivized bioenergy projects through positive financial incentives. These incentive schemes however are facing a downturn since 2014.

Yorkshire and the Humber is ISABEL’s *intermediately mature in biogas* region analysed. It is a regional community that is strongly orientated towards developing and generating its own bioenergy in the **United Kingdom**. It has a growing policy orientation towards the provision of financial incentives for public and private community energy projects and represents the second lowest unemployment rate. Legislation however, seems to indicate an unstable trend towards subsidies and tax reliefs for bioenergy initiatives.

Central and Eastern Macedonia & Thrace is ISABEL’s *preliminarily involved in biogas* region analysed. It is a very slowly developing bioenergy region. It is located in **Greece**, which currently represents the highest unemployment rate in Europe and the most critical political conditions of a financial crisis. Political instability and a relative lack of provision causes renewable energy projects to depend predominantly on private initiatives and enterprise interests.

Further the analysis of ISABEL’s three-targeted regions in terms of their “context & intervening conditions”, “causal conditions”, “approach, action and interaction strategy”, “methods & tools”, and “consequences after the implementation of the bioenergy project”), this report presents a pool of methods proposed for the successful **adoption and diffusion** of bioenergy initiatives. Strengths, weakness, opportunities and threats of these bioenergy projects has been analysed, with some of the biggest threats being **the lack of sufficient communication of the benefits of biogas community bioenergy, appropriate technologies within regions, initiator interest and financial security (due to changing policies and legislations or wider national financial conditions)**.

A key take-away from this report is the identified sequence in delivering a successful bioenergy project with a target to achieve a positive social impact, as follows:

¹⁰⁸ The latter “*biogas readiness*” has been developed by the INSEAD / ISABEL team to describe in a simple way the relative “*maturity in biogas*” and level (mature, intermediate, preliminary) at which each selected region appears to use biogas. This readiness depends upon interconnected factors, which may relate to national policies, governmental, investor needs, social, technical and other requirements. The three selected regions for analysis by ISABEL are stated below.

The challenge of this report has been to identify an appropriate approach the scaling and spreading complex and different bioenergy initiatives. Numerous models were reviewed and it has been identified that the project models, which reflect their essential characteristics are **hybrid mixed and complex**. **Social franchising strategies seem to** reflect the character and goals of community bioenergy initiatives triggered by social innovations. These strategies proposed the development of a process of social innovations by **creating affiliations between new partners, exchanging and disseminating ideas, promoting a social behavioural change and stimulating policy-making as well as changes in existing regulations**.

Although there is no "single prescription for success" of a project, it has been highlighted that (through D1.1 and D1.3) some important factors for **successful** community energy projects include the provision of a **motivation mix** that mostly target **social** (e.g. job opportunities) **and financial incentives** (e.g. energy ownership, tax-reliefs and subsidies) as well as of **environmental and regulation related ones**. Remarkably, while the availability of **technical** support of a bioenergy project; it does not seem to offer a stand-alone incentive for its initiation, delivery and success.

Promoting engagement through communicative participatory processes therefore can significantly raise awareness and public trust, which can thereafter lead to attracting investments for the given bioenergy community project. The benefits and opportunities of such initiatives should thus be communicated and presentations of successful examples of community bioenergy projects across Europe could act as "**role models**" for the future. Understanding that self-efficacy and energy self-sufficiency, through self-investing communities could empower communities to generate, manage and benefit financially from their incentives could offer a motive for their decision-making.

Good practices suggested would seem to combine local entrepreneurial activities (e.g. by farmers), municipalities, local authorities, academia and local businesses. Joining these and more can create networks and cooperatives. The benefit of such **cooperative memberships** is largely perceived to be socio-economic, with environmental elements as the base point of project development.

Cross-sector partnership and synergetic actions (i.e. learning from each other at a local, regional, national and global scale) can stimulate successful social innovation community energy projects. Stimulating communities to **generate and own** their energy supply chain, achieve **energy self-sufficiency**, promote **sustainable ecology**, and thereafter become **shareholders** of their local community biogas energy venture as well as increase their joint **profitability**, can also influence positively the successful initiation and spread of a bioenergy project. Specific methods are analysed in chapter 3. Cooperative ventures are based on equity, which helps make ethical the community investments and financing. Successful projects appeared to raise awareness and interest in alternative energy use and benefits, which could influence policy-making and finally stimulate systemic behavioural transformation as well as project franchising and future project initiation, continuation and investments.

Appendix 1: Social franchising

Social franchising requires the engagement of social enterprises (local businesses or organizations with a social purpose, e.g. NGOs).¹⁰⁹ Although social franchising operations and frameworks can vary considerably, their main principles are the same¹¹⁰.

Identifying a social franchisor/ enterprise

- That is an organization that can replicate a successful model of a social enterprise

Identifying a social franchisee/ enterprise

- This group can be composed by at least one independent enterprise, which has been replicated successfully by the franchisor

Identifying a common operational platform for all project partners/ franchisees

- Regulating and agreeing on the rights and obligations of all franchisees involved in the project
 - Targeting the project grant providers and important financial sources
-

¹⁰⁹ <http://www.socialfranchising.coop/what-is-social-franchising>

¹¹⁰ <http://www.socialfranchising.coop/what-is-social-franchising>